

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D9.1 POLYPHEM Data Management Plan

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SUMMARY	This document is the deliverable D9.1 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 9 (Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project results, Communication). The Data Management Plan outlines how the research data collected or generated during the execution of the project POLYPHEM and after it is completed will be handled. It describes what data will be collected/generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centers and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targasonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
API	Application Programming Interface
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
AVI	Microsoft proprietary format for compression of Audio and Video files
BMP	BitMap (open format for images)
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research (Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire)
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France)
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D	Deliverable
DLL	Dynamic Link Library
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNS	Domain Name System (or Server)
DOC	Document Microsoft text proprietary format
DOCX	Document Microsoft text in OpenXML standard
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTD	Document Type Definition
DWG	DraWinG (format used for technical drawings and plans)
DXF	Drawing eXchange Format
ELF	Executable and Linkable Format, open standard for executable files, functions, libraries
EMF	Enhanced Meta File, Microsoft proprietary format for image files
EPS	Encapsulated Post-Script
EU	European Union
EXE	Executable file
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GB	GigaBit (10 ⁹ bit)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIF	Graphics Interchange Format
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
INIST-CNRS	Institut de l'Information Scientifique et Technique du CNRS
ISO	International Standards Organization
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KB	KiloBit (10 ³ bit)
M	Mathworks (Matlab) proprietary format for command file
MARCXML	Machine-Readable Cataloging in eXtensible Markup Language
MAT	Mathworks (Matlab) proprietary format for data file
MB	MegaBit (10 ⁶ bit)
MOV	Apple proprietary format for video files
MP3	MPEG-1/2 audio layer III, open format for compressed audio files
MP4	MPEG-4, proprietary standard for encoding audio-visual objects
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
ODC	Open Document
ODF	Open Document Format for office applications, standard OASIS
ODG	Open Document Graphics, in ODF standard
ODP	Open Document Presentation, in ODF standard

ODS	Open Document Spreadsheet , in ODF standard
ODT	Open Document Text , in ODF standard
OpenXML	Open eXtensible Markup Language
ORA	OpenRaster (open format for graphical files using OpenXML standard)
PDF	Portable Document Format
PNG	Portable Network Graphic
PPS	Power Point Show , Microsoft proprietary format for viewing slides presentation
PPT	Microsoft Power Point presentation proprietary format
PPTX	Microsoft Power Point presentation in OpenXML standard
PSD	PhotoShop Document , Adobe proprietary format for image files
PU	Public
RAM	Real Media Audio Metadata file, closed format for audio files
RAR	Roshal Archive , closed file format for archiving of compressed data
REDIS	Remote Dictionary Server (open source software)
REST	Representational State Transfer protocol
RTF	Rich Text Format
SCOAP3	Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics
SGML	Standard Generalized Markup Language
STP	Closed format for 3D-computer aided design files record and interchange
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
TXT	Text
UTF	Universal character set Transformation Format
VSD	Visio Drawing file proprietary format
VSDX	Visio Drawing file format, in OpenXML standard
WAV	Waveform audio file open format
WMA	Windows Media Audio , Microsoft proprietary format for audio files
WMF	Windows Meta File , Microsoft proprietary format for image files
WMV	Windows Media Video , Microsoft proprietary format for video files
WP	Work Package
WPG	WordPerfect Graphics , closed format for graphical files
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface (software application)
XLS	Document Microsoft Excel proprietary format
XLSX	Document Microsoft Excel in OpenXML standard
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
ZIP	PKZIP (Phil Katz ZIP), open format for archiving of compressed data

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the Data management Plan (DMP) ruling data management within the H2020 EU funded project “Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle” (POLYPHEM – 764048). The aim of the document is to describe the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, generated and processed within the research activities of the POLYPHEM project. Among other, the document sets out:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project,
- the list of data collected, processed and generated,
- the methodology and standards to be applied,
- the data that will be made openly available and the procedure(s),
- the measures undertaken or to apply in order to facilitate the interoperability and reuse of the research data, and
- the rules of data curation and preservation.

In the frame of POLYPHEM, various types of research data are expected to be collected, processed and/or generated: data collected in previous scientific publications/patents, measuring data observed, design data created in the frame of the project, numerical simulation and processing tools, etc. As participants in the Open Research Data Pilot, for each one of those research data, the POLYPHEM partners will carefully study the possibility and pertinence to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, to the extent possible (FAIR).

The DMP will be regularly updated. This document has been prepared following the guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon 2020.

The Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) will be used as standard to build the database of the project results (data and metadata) in order to make them easy to find and to interoperate. The results will be preserved and made available in the repository Zenodo¹ which is referred to in the European network OpenAIRE².

The scheme presented in Figure 1 shows the principle of the data delivery, conservation and restitution using standards at each step of the data management process.

Figure 1: Scheme of the Data Management principle followed in POLYPHEM

¹ <https://about.zenodo.org/>

² OpenAIRE is a network of Open Access repositories, archives and journals that support Open Access policies. <https://www.openaire.eu>

This DMP is created and will be updated with the respect of all national and European legal requirements, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679)³. It also complies with the requirements of the article 29 of the Grant Agreement, specifically, in terms of obligation to disseminate results (art. 29.1 of GA), open access to scientific publications (art. 29.2 of GA) and open access to research data (art. 29.3 of GA). It also respects the IPR protection framework applicable to the project, potential conflicts of commercialization and dissemination of own results, as defined in the article 8.3 of the project Consortium Agreement signed by the beneficiaries.

The objective is to put useful information and recommendations on the management of the project results into a prospective, descriptive and upgradeable single document.

2. DATA SUMMARY

2.1 PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION

POLYPHEM will produce several datasets during the lifetime of the project. The nature of the data will be both quantitative and qualitative and will be analysed from a range of perspectives for project development and scientific purposes. The created datasets will have the same structure, in accordance with the guidelines of Horizon H2020 for the Data Management Plan.

The completion of the work plans associated to the 8 technical Work-Packages (WP) of POLYPHEM will generate new and original scientific and technical data. Some of these data will be created by a group of participants as a result of collaborative work, while others will be created by one specific partner in individual work. Data will also be collected in previous scientific publications or patents and will serve as reference cases, results or knowledge for new research developments.

The data collection, selection, classification and preservation is a critical action which will be maintained and carefully monitored all along the execution of the project. It will enable to exchange relevant technical information among the beneficiaries and therefore increase the efficiency of the collaborative research work for the achievement of the objectives of the project. The preservation of the data after the completion of the project will permit to continue some research by providing useful and re-usable information to the partners engaged in the long-term development of similar technologies. Technical specifications of instruments, components or processes, design of new components, lessons learned from observations and experimental operation will serve for conceptual improvements and future testing procedures without repeating the same work.

Finally, the data management aims at sharing public results with communities of professors, students, researchers, engineers, managers and policy makers, during and after the end of the project. This will contribute to increase the impact of the project in the short, mid and long-term.

2.2 CATEGORIES, TYPES, FORMATS AND SIZES OF DATA GENERATED OR COLLECTED

All the data generated or collected during the project POLYPHEM will be made available as electronic files (numerical files).

2.2.1 Categories

In general, the data will be classified into 4 categories, each of them contains sub-categories of datasets.

- Text-based data
 - Publication, article
 - Report, scientific survey
 - Experimental result (structured text)
 - Numerical simulation result (structured text)
 - Datasheet
 - Technical specification of instrument/process

³ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

- Audio-Visual data
 - Scientific and technical presentation
 - Poster
 - Flyer, leaflet
 - Picture, image, drawing, illustration
 - Scheme, sketch, diagram
 - Video
- Models
 - Design of component
 - Technical drawing, construction plan
 - Heat transfer model
 - Optical model
 - Thermo-mechanical model
 - Techno-economical model
- Software data
 - Script
 - Executable code
 - Source code
- Archives (compressed datasets)

2.2.2 Types

There are 2 types of electronic files: binary and ASCII (or Unicode).

A binary file is a series of bits with logical values 0 or 1 (or other derived logical values like True/False, etc...).

An ASCII file is made of series of characters encoded on 7 bits with the rules of the ASCII standard (ISO 646). Original ASCII standard is restricted to Latin characters (letters, numbers and signs), Unicode standard is used to extend ASCII to worldwide utilization.

2.2.3 Format

The format of a file is determined by the encoding system, or standard, used by the original software to generate the file. Proprietary formats (or closed formats) can only be read using the original software (or similar software) which are usually commercial products. Open formats can be read by both proprietary and free and open-source software. Open formats are also called free file formats if they are not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use them at no monetary cost for any desired purpose.

In POLYPHEM, the formats used to produce the data will tend to respect the international standards as they are defined by the International Standard for Archival Description (ISAD). Open formats will be preferred, to the possible extent, because they make the data more easily accessible and re-usable.

Each format is identified through an extension at the end of the filename. Extensions respect international standards and are presented in the form of 3 or 4-letters acronyms.

2.2.4 Size

The size of the datasets is generally in the range of KB to MB for the text-based data, models and software, and from MB to GB for the audio-visual data.

2.2.5 Summary: Document Type Definition

The basic parameters of the Document Type Definition (DTD) are summarized in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the document type definition (categories and formats of the datasets)

Category	Type	Open Format/extension	Closed Format/extension
Text based data	ASCII, Unicode	.odt, .docx, .rtf, .ods, .xlsx, .txt, .sgml, .xml, .csv	.doc, .xls
	binary	.pdf, .eps	
Audio-visual data	binary	.odp, .pptx, .odc, .ora, .bmp, .jpeg, .jpg, .png, .gif, .odg, .eps, .wav, .mp3, .mpeg	.pps, .ppt, .vsd, .psd, .tiff, .wpg, .wmf, .emf, .wma, .ram, .avi, .mov, .wmv, .mp4
Models	binary	.dwg, .eps	.dxf, .ora, .stp
Software data	binary	.exe, .dll	.elf, .m, .mat
Archives (compressed datasets)	binary	.zip	.rar

2.3 RE-USE OF DATA

The consortium of the POLYPHEM project already agreed on the access to data, ruled by the terms of section 9 of the Consortium Agreement.

(9.3- Access rights for implementation) *“Access rights to results [...] needed for the performance of the own work of a Party under the Project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis [...].”*

(9.4- Access rights for exploitation) *“Access rights to results if needed for exploitation of a Party's own results shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions. Access rights to results for internal research activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis”.*

Specific terms have been agreed for the access to software (section 9.8.3 of the CA)

“Access rights to software that is results shall comprise access to the object code; and, where normal use of such an object code requires an application programming interface (hereafter API), access to the object code and such an API; and, if a Party can show that the execution of its tasks under the Project or the exploitation of its own results is technically or legally impossible without access to the source code, access to the source code to the extent necessary.”

“Fraunhofer ISE refuses to provide source code or API in this Project and will not, in any case, access to another Party's source code or API, unless otherwise agreed individually.”

The consortium of the POLYPHEM project is encouraged to make existing data available for research. In general, the data (in total or in part), when it is made accessible to public, could be re-used by partners of POLYPHEM during and after the project, or by external researchers, for the following aims:

- Implementation of the work programme of the project (execution of the tasks by the partners).
- Training of students, researchers, engineers by partners or by external academic institutions.
- Implementation of other research works on CSP technologies by partners or by external bodies.

2.4 ORIGIN OF DATA

Most of the data will be originated by the POLYPHEM participants. Experimental results will be generated from experimental facilities, test-benches and from the operation of the prototype plant. Other data will be generated through the utilization of software tools for simulation, for design of components and processes. Text-based data will be produced by the partners in activities of reporting, design, processing of raw data. Audio-visual data will be generated by the partners for communication purposes or by external body under sub-contracting legal framework.

Previous CSP initiatives and projects worldwide in which solar tower or solar combined cycles data have been or still are collected will be the origin of the part of the POLYPHEM collected, processed and generated data.

2.5 DATA UTILITY

In general, the audience who might use data generated or collected in the project POLYPHEM are:

- The POLYPHEM Consortium;
- European Commission services, European Agencies, EU and national policy makers;
- Research institutions, universities, institutes, training centers across the Europe and worldwide;
- CSP and renewable energies related industries;
- Private and public investment sector.

Open research data from POLYPHEM will be useful to other researchers to underpin scientific publications by referring to the POLYPHEM results in surveys or by incorporating the POLYPHEM results in comparative analysis with their own project results.

More detailed description of the data and whom they might be useful to will be given later in updated versions of the Data Management Plan, since data collection and creation is an ongoing process.

3. FAIR DATA

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 Discoverability: metadata provision

The repository Zenodo complies with the principles of FAIR data. The best practices are implemented to make data findable (see <http://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

“(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier : A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.”

“Data are described with rich metadata [...]: Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema⁴ minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.”

“Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes : The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.”

“(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource : Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.”

A metadata template has been created for POLYPHEM consortium on the basis of the compulsory requirements of Zenodo in order to better describe, easily discover and trace the data collected and generated by the POLYPHEM project during the life and after the end of the action. The template includes the basic mandatory metadata required by the repository and additional metadata that could be optionally provided by the project consortium depending on the type and/or version of the research data uploaded, if appropriate. The template will be sent to the relevant partners to be filled in and stored at the Zenodo repository. The content of this template is listed in Table 2.

⁴ DataCite is an international consortium of libraries and services specialized in digital sciences, aiming at facilitating numerical archives and access to numerical resources on internet. See: <https://www.datacite.org/>

Table 2: Template of metadata for archiving the POLYPHEM datasets

Metadata	Category	Additional comments
Type of data	Mandatory	
DOI	Mandatory	If not filled, Zenodo will assign an automatic DOI. Please keep the same DOI if the document is already identified with a DOI.
Responsible / author(s)	Mandatory	
Title	Mandatory	
Publication date	Mandatory	
Date of repository submission	Mandatory	
Version	Mandatory	
Description	Mandatory	
Keywords	Mandatory	Frequently used keywords.
Size	Mandatory	The approximate size.
Access rights	Mandatory	Open Access. Other permissions can be applied, when appropriate.
Terms of Access Rights	Optional	Description of the Creative Common Licenses ⁵ . POLYPHEM will open the data under Attribution, ShareAlike and Non Commercial Licenses.
Communities	Mandatory	
Funding	Mandatory	European Union (EU), Horizon 2020, H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage, Grant N° 764048, POLYPHEM.

3.1.2 Identification of data

If the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of the publications has been already identified, the POLYPHEM consortium will maintain it to facilitate the identification of the data. In case of no DOI has been attributed to the publication or research outputs firstly, the partners comply to reserve the DOI generated by the repository.

3.1.3 Naming convention

No naming convention is foreseen in the POLYPHEM data management.

Version numbers will be provided in the metadata table accompanying the updated version of the file uploaded.

⁵ Creative Commons licenses, set by the organization Creative Commons, rule the conditions of distribution and reuse of original documents/data. <https://creativecommons.org/>

3.1.4 Search keywords

The keywords search option will be provided to optimize the possibility of data re-use and facilitate the discoverability of the data in the Zenodo repository.

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 Types of data made openly available

According to the article 26 of the GA, the partners who have generated the research outputs are the owners of the generated data and have right to disseminate its results as long as there is no legitimate purpose or need to protect the results. Each dissemination action should be noticed in advance to the other partners at least 45 days beforehand and accompanied by sufficient information on the results to disseminate (Art. 29.1 of GA).

As soon as the research data is generated and ready to be uploaded, it should be deposited in the repository Zenodo. The underlying data of the scientific publications should be uploaded not later than the relevant publication (Art.29.3 of GA). However, the consortium has the right to not make research results public in order to protect it. In this case, the non-public data will be archived at the repository under either “closed” or “restricted” depending of the allowed access rights. Please see the 3.4 “Increase data re-use” sub-section for further details.

3.2.2 Deposition of data

The created data and accompanying metadata will be deposited at the Zenodo repository and stored in JSON-format according to a defined JSON-schema⁶. Metadata is exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core⁷, and DataCite Metadata Schema (according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines). Zenodo’s policies are described in the web-page <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>. The information is also given in annex 1.

Several communities already exist in Zenodo. The POLYPHEM consortium proposes to define and create in Zenodo an additional community identified as potential users of the data generated or collected in the project. The scientific and technical scope of this community will cover all aspects of concentrated solar energy and its applications like solar power generation, solar fuels, high temperature solar process heat, solar thermal water desalination.

A few existing communities encompassing the scope of POLYPHEM will tentatively be associated to the targeted users of the POLYPHEM datasets, like among others:

- Renewable Energy Potential
- Power Trading Agent Competition
- Continental Journal of renewable Energy
- International Journal of Renewable Energy and Environmental Engineering
- Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (CREC)

3.2.3 Methods needed to access the data

All metadata is openly available in Zenodo under Creative Commons licenses, and all open content is openly accessible through open APIs. In line with the FAIR data guidelines, Zenodo does its best effort to make data accessible (see <http://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

« (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol : Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. »

« The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable: [...] OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web. »

« The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary: Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it. »

⁶ JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows to annotate and validate JSON documents

⁷ The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative is an open organization supporting innovation in metadata design and best practices across the metadata ecology. <http://dublincore.org/>

« Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available: Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least. Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself. »

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

In order to make the research outputs and underlying data generated within the POLYPHEM project interoperable, the consortium will use data in the standard formats and prioritize the available (open) software, whenever possible. The consortium will also respect the common standards officially applied to the various formats that will be used for the data.

The repository Zenodo is organized and managed in order to make data interoperable, to the maximum extent, in agreement with the FAIR data rules and recommendations (see <http://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

« (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation: Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. »

« (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles: For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition⁸), funders (FundRef⁹) and grants (OpenAIRE). »

« (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data: Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL. »

Moreover, in order to further enhance the data exchange and re-use between researchers, organizations, institutions, countries and other, the consortium intends also encourage Zenodo community to perform as far as possible a follow-up of the POLYPHEM data re-used by other community participants for retracing the derivatives works based on the re-used data. The aim is to make this interoperability data concept viable through the possibility and utility of consultation of the results of the re-used POLYPHEM data to enrich and stimulate further scientific reflexions.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES)

All the openly accessible data and corresponding metadata uploaded on Zenodo will be available for re-use, including after the end of the project. The publication and underlying data will be also uploaded in compliance with the 6-month embargo allowed by the EC. Moreover, the POLYPHEM research data uploaded on Zenodo, excepting the data uploaded under closed, embargoed or restricted access, will be in open access under the Creative Commons Licenses: Attribution, ShareAlike, Non Commercial, and No Derivatives. For the POLYPHEM data, only three first license types will be applied (see Table 3):

Table 3: Creative Commons licenses used for the diffusion and re-use of POLYPHEM data

Chosen Licenses	Icon	Meaning	Abbreviation
	Attribution: Permits all uses of the original work, as long as it is attributed to the original author.	BY	
		Non-commercial: License does not permit any commercial use of the original work.	NC
		Share Alike: Any derivative work should use the same license as the original work.	SA

⁸ The Open Definition sets out principles that define “openness” in relation to data and content. <https://opendefinition.org/>

⁹ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

Although the consortium is encouraged to extend the open access to the data and will contribute to this to the extent possible, it reserves the right of upload data in the repository under justified restricted access as well as to keep it as such after the end of the project.

In this regard, during the lifetime of the project, the sharing of the files under restricted access will be possible only with the consent of the depositor or author of their original version. The description of the potential “restricted” data as well as reasons explaining this choice of the consortium will be detailed in the next versions of the DMP clarified by the particularities of the implemented project research activities and evaluation of the potential impact of the open status of the results by the partners.

According to the Zenodo policy, the files under the closed access will be protected against any unauthorised access at all levels.

As for the files under embargo status, the end data of the embargo will be compulsorily provided. The allowed 6-month embargo period for the publications and underlying data will be respected. The access to the embargoed data will be restricted until the end of embargo period and will be open automatically after the end of the embargo period.

After the end of the project, uploaded data will be preserved in the repository regardless the access mode. The responsible partner(s) reserve the possibility to make the “closed” and “restricted” data openly accessible after the end of the project on the consent of the relevant partners if their confidentiality considerations change.

Zenodo contributes to make the data reusable through the following rules and practices (see <http://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

« *(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes : Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments. »*

« *(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license : License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to a Open Definition license : Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader. »*

« *(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance : All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work. »*

« *(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards : Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available. »*

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The research data collected, generated and/or processed and project research outputs will be uploaded and preserved during and after the end of the project in the Zenodo repository. The repository allows uploading data free of charge with the size limited to up to 50 GB per record. The data will be stored indefinitely (minimum 5 years). Currently there are no costs for preserving data in this repository and, thus, no costs have been foreseen to these matters by the project. If any unforeseen costs related to the open access of research data occur, it is possible to be charged on the Program given its eligibility status for reimbursement, according to the articles 6 and 6.2 of GA.

Moreover, each partner has devoted its own human resources to respect the prescriptions set out by the deliverable D9.1 “Data Management Plan”. CNRS remains the partner responsible for the management and supervision of the management of the data within the POLYPHEM project, including data verification before uploading, uploaded data updating and so on. The costs of the personnel assigned to the data management have been foreseen in the initial project budget estimation and is considered as to be charged on the Program.

Also, as required by the article 18 of the GA, all the records and data will be preserved internally by the consortium during five years after the project. The openly accessible, restricted and closed data shared through the repository will be preserved after the end of the project. The access for the restricted and closed data status will be possible through the express request of access addressed to the POLYPHEM project coordinator.

5. DATA SECURITY

The public repository Zenodo has been selected as a long-term secure storage of the POLYPHEM project research outputs given its features fulfilling technical and legal data security requirements and long term preservation. Please consult the terms at <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/> and repository's features at <https://help.zenodo.org/features/>.

The data will also be stored internally on the POLYPHEM project intranet. No access external to the consortium will be possible. Further details on the security storage of the data collected, generated and processed within the project are available in the deliverable D10.1 "Project Management Handbook".

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

There are no ethical issues affecting to the POLYPHEM project research activities. Thus, no specific ethical considerations should be applied to the data sharing within the project.

However, while sharing any openly accessible data, the POLYPHEM consortium will respect the relevant requirements described in the deliverable D11.1 "POPD – Requirement No.1" and apply the rule of noticing to the partners the intention of dissemination of any project related data at least 45 days beforehand according to the article 29.1 of the GA. Moreover, the consortium will respect the obligations mentioned in the article 34.1 of the GA "Ethics and Research Integrity", in particular those related to the compliance with:

- Ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity), and
- Applicable national, EU and international law,

during the implementation of the project.

7. ANNEX

7.1 ZENODO GENERAL POLICIES

The following information is extracted from the Zenodo website (see: <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)

7.1.1 Content

- **Scope:** All fields of research. All types of research artefacts. Content must not violate privacy or copyright, or breach confidentiality or non-disclosure agreements for data collected from human subjects.
- **Status of research data:** Any status is accepted, from any stage of the research lifecycle.
- **Eligible depositors:** Anyone may register as user of Zenodo. All users are allowed to deposit content for which they possess the appropriate rights.
- **Ownership:** By uploading content, no change of ownership is implied and no property rights are transferred to CERN. All uploaded content remains the property of the parties prior to submission.
- **Data file formats:** All formats are allowed - even preservation unfriendly. Zenodo is working on guidelines and features that will help people deposit in preservation friendly formats.
- **Volume and size limitations:** Total files size limit per record is 50GB. Higher quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis.
- **Data quality:** All information is provided "as-is", and the user shall hold Zenodo and information providers supplying data to Zenodo free and harmless in connection with the use of such information.
- **Metadata types and sources:** All metadata is stored internally in JSON-format according to a defined [JSON schema](#). Metadata is exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema (according to the [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#)).
- **Language:** For textual items, English is preferred but all languages are accepted.

- **Licenses:** Users must specify a license for all publicly available files. Licenses for closed access files may be specified in the description field.

7.1.2 Access and Reuse

- **Access to data objects:** Files may be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. Files deposited under closed access are protected against unauthorized access at all levels. Access to metadata and data files is provided over standard protocols such as HTTP and OAI-PMH.
- **Use and re-use of data objects:** Use and re-use is subject to the license under which the data objects were deposited.
- **Embargo status:** Users may deposit content under an embargo status and provide an end date for the embargo. The repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publically available automatically.
- **Restricted Access:** Users may deposit restricted files with the ability to share access with others if certain requirements are met. These files will not be made publicly available and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of depositor of the original file.
- **Metadata access and reuse:** Metadata is licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.

7.1.3 Removal

- **Revocation:** Content not considered to fall under the scope of the repository will be removed and associated DOIs issued by Zenodo revoked. Please signal promptly, ideally no later than 24 hours from upload, any suspected policy violation. Alternatively, content found to already have an external DOI will have the Zenodo DOI invalidated and the record updated to indicate the original external DOI. User access may be revoked on violation of Terms of Use.
- **Withdrawal:** If the uploaded research object must later be withdrawn, the reason for the withdrawal will be indicated on a tombstone page, which will henceforth be served in its place. Withdrawal is considered an exceptional action, which normally should be requested and fully justified by the original uploader. In any other circumstance reasonable attempts will be made to contact the original uploader to obtain consent. The DOI and the URL of the original object are retained.

7.1.4 Longevity

- **Versions:** Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and record are preserved.
- **Replicas:** All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- **Retention period:** Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- **Functional preservation:** Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- **File preservation:** Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- **Fixity and authenticity:** All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- **Succession plans:** In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

7.2 ZENODO INFRASTRUCTURE

The following information is extracted from the Zenodo website (see: <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>)

7.2.1 Organisational

- Host institution

Zenodo is hosted by CERN which has existed since 1954 and currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20+ years. CERN is a memory institution for High Energy Physics and renowned for its pioneering work in Open Access. Organisationally Zenodo is embedded in the IT Department, Collaboration Devices and Applications Group, Digital Repositories Section (IT-CDA-DR).

Zenodo is offered by CERN as part of its mission to make available the results of its work (CERN Convention, Article II, §1).

- Legal status

CERN is an intergovernmental organisation and has legal personality in the metropolitan territories of all CERN Member States (CERN Convention, Article IX) and enjoys the corresponding legal capacity under public international law.

As an intergovernmental organization CERN enjoys certain privileges and immunities, including e.g. immunity from jurisdiction of the national courts to ensure Zenodo independence from individual Member States. This does not mean that CERN operate in some kind of legal vacuum as protocols requires that CERN settle its disputes by other means.

- Legal documents:
 - CERN Convention
 - Protocol on the privileges and immunities of the European Organization for Nuclear Research

7.2.2 Funding

Zenodo is funded by:

- European Commission via the OpenAIRE projects:
 - FP7: OpenAIRE (246686), OpenAIREplus (283595)
 - Horizon 2020: OpenAIRE2020 (643410), OpenAIRE-Connect (731011) and OpenAIRE-Advance (777541).
- CERN
- Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
- Donations via CERN & Society Foundation

Zenodo is developed and supported as a marginal activity, and hosted on top of existing infrastructure and services at CERN, in order to reduce operational costs and rely on existing efforts for High Energy Physics. CERN has some of the world's top experts in running large scale research data infrastructures and digital repositories that Zenodo relies on in order to deliver a trusted digital repository.

7.2.3 Memberships

CERN is an active member of the following organisations and international bodies (non-exhaustive):

- DataCite
- ORCID¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://orcid.org/>

- FORCE11¹¹ (in particular Data Citation Principles and Software Citation Principles)
- Research Data Alliance
- SCOAP3¹²

Zenodo is partner in multiple European Commission funded projects, amongst others:

- OpenAIRE
- EUDAT¹³

7.2.4 Technical

Zenodo is powered by CERN Data Centre and the Invenio¹⁴ digital library framework and is fully run on open source products all the way through.

Physically, Zenodo's entire technical infrastructure is located on CERN's premises which is subject to CERN's legal status (see above).

- Server management

The Zenodo servers are managed via OpenStack¹⁵ and Puppet¹⁶ configuration management system which ensures that Zenodo servers always have the latest security patches applied. Servers are monitored via CERN's monitoring infrastructure based on Flume¹⁷, Elasticsearch¹⁸, Kibana¹⁹ and Hadoop²⁰. Application errors are logged and aggregated in a local Sentry²¹ instance. Traffic to Zenodo front-end servers is load balanced via a combination of DNS load balancing and HAProxy²² load balancers.

Zenodo is furthermore running two independent systems: one production system and one quality assurance system. This ensures that all changes, whether at infrastructure level or source code level, can be tested and validated on Zenodo quality assurance system prior to being applied to Zenodo production system.

- Front-end servers

Zenodo front-end servers are responsible for running the Invenio repository platform application which is based on Python and the Flask web development framework. The front-end servers are running nginx²³ HTTP server and uWSGI application server in front of the application and nginx is in addition in charge of serving static content.

- Data storage

All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service²⁴ in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers.

¹¹ <https://www.force11.org/>

¹² <https://scoap3.org/>

¹³ <https://eudat.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://invenio-software.org/>

¹⁵ Open source software for creating private and public clouds. <https://www.openstack.org/>

¹⁶ <https://puppet.com>

¹⁷ Flume is a distributed service for collecting, aggregating, and moving large amounts of log data. <https://flume.apache.org/>

¹⁸ Elasticsearch is an open source software under Apache License for index and search of data. <https://www.elastic.co/fr/>

¹⁹ Kibana allows to visualize data within Elasticsearch environment. <https://www.elastic.co/fr/products/kibana>

²⁰ The Apache Hadoop software library is a framework that allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers. <https://hadoop.apache.org/>

²¹ Open-source error tracking software tool. <https://sentry.io/welcome/>

²² Open source software, load balancer and proxy server. <http://www.haproxy.org/>

²³ nginx [engine x] is an HTTP and reverse proxy server, a mail proxy server, and a generic TCP/UDP proxy server. <https://nginx.org/en/>

²⁴ <http://eos.web.cern.ch/content/about-eos>

For each file Zenodo stores two independent MD5 checksums. One checksum is stored by Invenio, and used to detect changes to files made from outside of Invenio. The other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks.

Zenodo may, depending on access patterns in the future, move the archival and/or the online copy to CERN's offline long-term tape storage system CASTOR in order to minimize long-term storage costs.

EOS is the primary low latency storage infrastructure for physics data from the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and CERN currently operates multiple instances totalling 150+ petabytes of data with expected growth rates of 30-50 petabytes per year. CERN's CASTOR system currently manages 100+ petabytes of LHC data which are regularly checked for data corruption.

Invenio provides an object store like file management layer on top of EOS which is in charge of e.g. version changes to files.

- Metadata storage

Metadata and persistent identifiers in Zenodo are stored in a PostgreSQL instance operated on CERN's Database on Demand infrastructure with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week. Metadata is in addition indexed in an Elasticsearch cluster for fast and powerful searching. Metadata is stored in JSON format in PostgreSQL in a structure described by versioned JSON-Schemas. All changes to metadata records on Zenodo are versioned, and happening inside database transactions.

In addition to the metadata and data storage, Zenodo relies on Redis²⁵ for caching and RabbitMQ²⁶ and Python Celery²⁷ for distributed background jobs.

7.2.5 Security

We take security very serious and do our best to protect your data.

- CERN Data Centre:

The Zenodo data centre is located on CERN premises and all physical access is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties (e.g. Zenodo staff do not have physical access to the CERN Data Centre) .

- Servers:

The Zenodo servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning e.g. remote access to Zenodo servers are restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via Zenodo automatic configuration management system Puppet.

- Network:

CERN Security Team runs both host and network based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern and contents into and out of CERN networks in order to detect attacks. All access to zenodo.org happens over HTTPS, except for static documentation pages which are hosted on GitHub²⁸ pages.

- Data:

Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms (currently PBKDF2+SHA512). Users' access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application's secret key.

- Application:

²⁵ Redis is an open source in-memory data structure store, used as a database, cache and message broker. <https://redis.io/>

²⁶ Open source message broker [Mozilla public license]. <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

²⁷ Celery is a task queue implementation for Python web applications used to execute work outside the HTTP request-response cycle. <https://www.fullstackpython.com/celery.html>

²⁸ <https://github.com/>

Zenodo is employing a suite of techniques to protect the user's session from being stolen by an attacker when he is logged in and run vulnerability scans against the application.

- Staff:

CERN staff with access to user data operate under CERN Operational Circular no. 5, meaning among other things that

- staff should not exchange among themselves information acquired unless it is expressly required for the execution of their duties.
- access to user data must always be consistent with the professional duties and only permitted for resolution of problems, detection of security issues, monitoring of resources and similar.
- staff are liable for damage resulting from any infringement and can have access withdrawn and/or be subject to disciplinary or legal proceedings depending on seriousness of the infringement.

7.2.6 Special note on closed access data

Zenodo allows users to upload files under closed access. Closed access means that zenodo.org users will not be able to access the files you uploaded. The files are however stored unencrypted and may be viewed by Zenodo operational staff under specific conditions. This means that "closed access" on Zenodo is not suitable for secret or confidential data.